

CLASSIFICATION OF CONFLICTS AND DEVELOPMENT TENDENCIES OF CONFLICT SCIENCE

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Humanity is so wounded that it lives and struggles in the midst of various conflicts. The existence of conflicts, on the one hand, encourages humanity to fight, to improve its life, society, and state activities, and on the other hand, it also leads to the activation of various destructive and destructive forces. The parties' lack of understanding of each other, failure to come to any compromise, moves these forces. Conflict is a complex, multifaceted and multi-level socio-psychological condition. Conflict means, first of all, a struggle for values and a certain status, power, reserves, material and moral damage by opponents, and destruction of the opponent. Individuals, social groups, national-ethnic communities, states, a group of countries, united by one or another topic, interest and interests, participate in conflicts. This science also studies the internal conflicts of a person.

Conflicts arise for various reasons, namely: spiritual, material, economic, political, religious disagreements, etc. For a deeper understanding of the conflict, it is necessary to study the reasons for its origin. For example, conflicts between a leader and an employee in the workplace are usually caused by the fact that the leader does not have complete knowledge of management, does not know the field, cannot agree with subordinates, does not understand them, or cannot convey his message, etc. At the root of any conflict is the action of a party to achieve a certain goal. So, conflict is a unique quality of interaction aimed at achieving certain interests and goals.

Any conflict is a product of contradictions in the mental state of people and the individual. Every object and event in existence has contradictions of one form or another. Conflict arises on the basis of mutual exclusion of opposite properties and characteristics. The conflict, of course, creates the need to move to another state, stage, quality. Signs of a conflict are determined by the existence of a situation accepted by the participants of the conflict, the contentiousness of the object of the conflict, and the readiness of the participants to engage in the conflict to achieve their goals.

For many years, organizational conflicts have been viewed as a negative situation and efforts have been made to create a conflict-free organization and a conflict-free community. But today it has been proven that life is not without conflicts. Effective management of a group, community, state is manifested in the presence of conflicts, which helps to bring out shortcomings. In this case, the conflict becomes constructive, creative and serves as a factor in making the right decision. But in this case, the parties to the conflict, that is, the opponents, having their own opinions, must come to a decision without deviating from moral standards.

Dysfunctional (destructive) conflicts lead to a decrease in personal satisfaction, loss of group cooperation. This type of conflict arises from one party's only approval of its opinion,

lack of desire to compromise and agreement, insulting the other party, disregarding his opinion, striving to show his superiority.

The object of the conflict is the value that causes the conflict of interests. A conflict arises only if it has an object. Such objects can be real, potential, false and imaginary.

The subject of the conflict is the contradictions of the interacting parties, which they want to resolve through competition.

The impact of positive and negative manifestations of conflict on team activity can be seen in the following tables.

Positive	Negative
It leads to a softening of the situation between the conflicting parties	The emergence of material costs and emotional stress when participating in conflict situations
Get new information about opponents	Occurrence of staff turnover, increase in employee absenteeism
The unity of the team in the fight against external opponents	Discipline loosening, deterioration of social and spiritual environment in the team
Encouraging change and development in the group	Obsession with the process to the point of negatively impacting work
Disappearance of subordination syndrome in employees	Diminishing cooperation after the conflict is resolved. Decreased trust of employees towards each other
The introduction of new technologies into the work process, the revival of the incentive to promote new ideas	The emergence of difficulties in the restoration of relations at work

When classifying conflicts, it is necessary to take into account their uniqueness. From this point of view, it is: internal conflicts and struggle of the individual; interpersonal; between the individual and the group; intergroup; it is possible to divide into interstate (or coalitions of states) conflicts.

Internal conflict in a person arises as a result of his nervousness, dissatisfaction with his life activity, inability to come to a decision. For example, according to Sigmund Freud's theory of psychoanalysis, internal conflict originates from "I" and "High self-esteem." These conflicts have a psychological basis and arise from a person's low or very high self-esteem. They have a constructive and destructive character and can have a negative impact on the mental and physical condition of a person. For example, a student of a higher educational institution feels that, according to his existing knowledge, he should already work in an organization or enterprise as a mature specialist, or study for a doctorate. But since he has not yet graduated from a university and does not have a diploma in hand, he is depressed, and as a student, he strives to find a better job that is equal to his level. Or a person is not satisfied with the development of the society in which he lives. He wants to move to another developed country, but his financial situation does not allow it. As a result, the internal conflict that arises in him leads him to different paths (seeking to find a good job, working on himself, quarreling with relatives about money, taking a loan, etc.).

Interpersonal conflict. It is a conflict between two or more people, and it often occurs in life for various reasons. An example of this is a disagreement between a manager and an employee, a conflict between neighbors, a misunderstanding between passengers of public transport, etc. Such conflicts can occur in every aspect of society: economic, social, political, spiritual, and others. In interpersonal conflicts, the personal qualities of people, their mental potential, and upbringing are important.

Conflict between the individual and the group. Groups embody a number of relationships and necessarily have formal and informal leaders. Because of this, the risk of conflict within the group increases. Conflict between an individual and a group can be constructive or destructive. In the first case, it serves to strengthen the relationship between the individual and the group, and in the second case, it leads to disunity between the group.

Intergroup conflict. This conflict arises as a result of conflicting interests of different groups. In most cases, such conflicts occur within social groups. For example, among school classes, groups of students, HE departments, political parties, ethnic communities, religious organizations.

According to statistics, the main conflicts in the world are intergroup. These include mainly ethnic, racial, religious and cultural conflicts. In many cases, conflicts arise as a result of not satisfying the elementary needs of ethnic groups, that is, they are not given a certain status, cultural identity, freedom of thought, speech, and religion.

Interstate conflict. It is observed that such conflicts mainly arise as a result of disagreements between individual states and coalitions. Their reasons can be different, i.e. economic, political, ideological, territorial and others.

It should be said that all the types of conflicts listed above are always in contact with each other and have the power of interaction. For example, international conflicts in many cases affect the internal conflicts of the state, and the state affects the conflict between groups, and groups affect the conflict between individuals and groups.

Other types of conflicts. Of course, the above classification of conflicts is not complete. Today, they can be divided according to several signs.

Depending on people's life activities: household; family; by labor teams and types; military; educational and pedagogical, etc.

Depending on the nature of the objects from which conflicts arise: reserved; status-role; socio-cultural; ideological and others.

On the distribution of influence and tasks: "vertical" conflicts (leader - employee, higher organization - lower organization); "horizontal" conflicts (between leaders of the same status, between colleagues).

According to the difference in essence: constructive and destructive; short and long; realistic and unrealistic; local, regional and international.

From a philosophical point of view, it is possible to determine its general and partial manifestations, depending on the scale of manifestation of the conflict in a certain form and the width of its distribution. General conflict includes conflicts that arise and exist in all areas, subjects and events. For example, black and white, bad and good, virtue and ignorance, war and peace, etc. Subtle conflicts are contradictions that have their own characteristics in nature, society and human activity. For example, in nature - body and space, attraction and repulsion, association (unification) and dissociation (separation, dispersion), in society - conflicting property relations, differences and contradictions between personal, group and

social interests, in the field of knowledge - practice and theory, are conflicts between emotional and logical cognition.

The conflicts described above are always interrelated and are manifested through the interaction of social subjects with each other. Consciousness is necessary for the origin of conflict, therefore it is wrong to include life manifestations in the inorganic world among full-fledged conflicts. For example, change of seasons, water erosion of rock, melting of snow or ice in heat, etc. Also, the struggle of animals for survival cannot be included in such conflicts. After all, this is to maintain the vital level of one's organism in order to survive. Therefore, the basis of conflicts is primarily the conflict of interests and goals.

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